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"THE LAST DANCE OF THE SEASONS' SONG"

After my song was sang
I sat down and suddenly looked at him
He gave a smile and he's stranger to me
I have no idea who this man is, it's not clear because my eyes are too blurry

One scorching hot day
As I strolled along the way
There's this man again, our path crossing, he smiled but ignored
I can't see it clearly, my vision is blurry

Dusk came , as I faintly humming I went back my way
I searched for my umbrella, wondering where I'd misplaced it
I forgot, I was out of my mind that I'm holding it all along and nightfall caught me
And as I headed home, I stumbled and I eas like " ouch! that hurt!"